

Assessing the Reliability of InSAR Ground Displacement Products: The Role of Time Inconsistencies in Sequences of Multi-look Interferograms

Francesco Falabella^a, Antonio Pepe^a

^a Institute for Electromagnetic Sensing of the Environment (IREA), National Research Council (CNR) of Italy, Via Diocleziano 328, Napoli 80124

Abstract

Assessing the reliability of ground displacement products estimated using Multi-temporal InSAR (Mt-InSAR) algorithms is not trivial when only measured interferometric data are available; typically, external independent measurements are lacking and, if any, only for sparse points in space. Thus, data-driven methodologies working on complex InSAR data are usually adopted to characterize the precisions of InSAR estimates by computing the interferometric covariance matrix. Likewise, time inconsistencies arising in sequences of multi-look (ML) SAR interferograms, which have undergone at least one independent processing step (such as multi-look, filtering, phase-unwrapping), introduce other spurious signals that further affect the reliability of estimates. Among these contributions, some can be treated stochastically and others deterministically. We propose a statistical covariance-based approach to quantify the uncertainties introduced by decorrelation noise and phase-unwrapping errors. Instead, the deterministic terms resulting from time inconsistencies are compensated for using a recently developed phase bias compensation method. Some experimental results have been conducted by applying the methodologies to Sentinel-1 data over an area between the Basilicata and Campania regions in southern Italy. Eventually, we analyze the effectiveness of the methods by inspecting the achieved results and pointing out some limitations that should be overcome in the future.

1 Introduction

Synthetic aperture radar interferometry (InSAR) [1] has become a standardized technique since its first application in the late 1980s to measure ground deformation episodes by exploiting satellite SAR images. InSAR techniques have evolved considerably in recent years, and today, the SAR community can rely on a plethora of multi-temporal InSAR techniques (Mt-InSAR) [2], [3] that allow the temporal evolution of the ground deformation field to be tracked, which are suitable for various geophysical and electromagnetic characteristics of the investigated targets. These algorithms provide highly reliable results when the studied areas are not severely impacted by decorrelation noise [4]. In contrast, the degree of reliability of deformation estimates should be evaluated for each investigated target. Not only decorrelation problems introduce a deviation from the true desired geophysical signals, but also other processing mistakes or inaccurate compensations, such as phase-unwrapping (PhU) errors (potentially unavoidable), topographic residuals, orbital effects, residual atmospheric phase screen, and other higher-order terms. Along with the previous ones, a systematic phase bias on deformation field estimation has recently been observed when adopting networks consisting exclusively of ML interferograms with reduced temporal baseline (mainly in the order of 30 days or less) as opposed to the same estimation but made with interferograms with a larger baseline [5]; these sources of deviation have several sources and among them can be attributed to soil moisture [6]–[8] that could be mixed with the deformation. As just mentioned, small-baseline (SB) multi-look (ML) SAR interferogram networks could experience these geophysical contributions [6]–[8], especially in interferograms with small temporal

baseline, resulting in biased estimates of the ground deformation field [5]. However, using SB ML InSAR networks that do not satisfy the irrotational temporal constraint between phases is advantageous, as these time inconsistencies can help detect and mitigate these biased phases [9]–[11]. Yet, these time inconsistencies, which alter the reliability of the Mt-InSAR products, are also the result of PhU errors and decorrelation artefacts.

In this work, we focus on understanding the implications of time inconsistencies by first considering the stochastic part by deriving the InSAR covariance matrices of decorrelation noise and the time inconsistencies of PhU errors, using an SB-based approach through directional statistics and Heteroskedasticity-consistent estimators, respectively. Then, the deterministic side responsible for phase bias [5] is briefly addressed and compensated for using the methods proposed in [9]. We also show some results highlighting the potential of covariance matrix methods and the effectiveness of phase bias compensation. A set of 385 Sentinel-1 (S-1) A/B descending data covering the period from 2014 to 2022 has been used. Further experiments are also expected by the time of publication of the EUSAR full paper. In addition, insights into outstanding issues and the potential of time inconsistencies are provided.

2 InSAR Covariances due to Decorrelation effects

Decorrelation noise is undoubtedly one of the major causes of uncertainty in Mt-InSAR analyses. One way to quantify the amount of uncertainty for each measured interferogram is computing the InSAR variances and also the covariances between different interferograms. InSAR variances can be estimated by solving non-trivial integral forms [12], further

assuming zero correlation between different InSAR phases. Instead, working on the measured complex InSAR data and leveraging on decorrelation models, a compact notation for populating the “true” InSAR covariance matrix was given in [13], [14]. The formulation is valid under the assumption of complex circular Gaussian (CCG) distribution for the complex interferograms. It reduces to the well-known Cramér-Rao bound, when the covariance is evaluated for the same interferogram. The latter formulation for covariances also required to compute the other mutual interferograms. For this reason, the method in [13] does not fit perfectly with SB methods, which instead try to limit the generation of interferograms, focusing on the most coherent ones.

2.1 A Small Baseline-oriented approach

In this subsection, we propose a strategy to compute the InSAR covariance matrix using wrapped SB interferograms only; the method deeply uses the theory of directional statistics [15] and was recently detailed in a recently submitted work. Thus, the wrapped phases result from the superposition of L independent random samples within the resolution cell Θ : $\Delta\phi_m = \angle \left\{ \frac{1}{L} \sum_{\Theta} \exp[j\Delta\phi_m^{(\Theta)}] \right\}$, for $m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$. More generally, the sine and cosine of wrapped InSAR phases can be characterized with zero-mean multi-samples von Mises distributions $VM(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_{sin})$ and $VM(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_{cos})$, for the sine $S_m = \sum_{\Theta} \sin[\Delta\phi_m^{(\Theta)}]$ and cosine $C_m = \sum_{\Theta} \cos[\Delta\phi_m^{(\Theta)}]$ terms, respectively. Hence, following these statistical assumptions, it can be demonstrated that, for high-concentration parameters $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ [15], the interferometric variance terms can be characterized as follows:

$$\text{var}\{\Delta\phi_m\} \approx \frac{1}{L\kappa_m} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2\kappa_m} \right). \quad (1)$$

Observing that $\text{var}\{\alpha - \beta\} = \text{var}\{\alpha\} + \text{var}\{\beta\} - 2\text{cov}\{\alpha, \beta\}$ and using (1), the covariance between the two generic interferograms α and β follows as:

$$\text{cov}\{\Delta\phi_{\alpha}, \Delta\phi_{\beta}\} = \frac{1}{2L} \left[\frac{1}{\kappa_{\alpha}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2\kappa_{\alpha}} \right) + \frac{1}{\kappa_{\beta}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2\kappa_{\beta}} \right) - \frac{1}{\kappa_{\alpha\beta}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2\kappa_{\alpha\beta}} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

where the concentration parameters $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ [15] are easily substituted and approximated by the same ones obtained with maximum likelihood estimates (MLE) $\hat{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}$, for instance, by using one of the approximations proposed in [16], and in particular, the following formula can be adopted:

$$\hat{\kappa}_m \approx (1.28 - 0.53\hat{\rho}_m^2) \tan\left(\frac{\pi\hat{\rho}_m}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{\rho}_m = \left| \frac{1}{L} \sum_{\Theta} \exp[j\Delta\phi_m^{(\Theta)}] \right|$ is the mean resultant length of the m -th wrapped InSAR phases. It is computed assuming the ergodicity condition and calculating the MLEs considering a group of pixels nearby a given SAR pixel enclosed by the spatial box $\hat{\Theta}$. It is worth noting that

the jointly maximum likelihood concentration parameter $\hat{\kappa}_{\alpha\beta}$ in (2) is always obtained using (3), taking into account the following mean resultant length $\hat{\rho}_{\alpha\beta} = \left| \frac{1}{L} \sum_{\Theta} \exp \left[j \left(\Delta\phi_{\alpha}^{(\Theta)} - \Delta\phi_{\beta}^{(\Theta)} \right) \right] \right|$. The adopted directional-based statistical formalism can be applied to characterizing distributed and permanent scatterers targets.

3 Time inconsistencies in Mt-InSAR Analyses

Any closed loop of InSAR phases formed in the temporal dimension should satisfy the irrotational condition, but when this condition is violated, time inconsistencies occur. If we form a loop of three arcs, a nonclosure triplet of unwrapped SAR interferograms is obtained as follows:

$$\Delta\phi_{\alpha} + \Delta\phi_{\beta} + \Delta\phi_{\gamma} \neq 0 \quad (4)$$

where α , β , and γ are three generic temporally connected SAR interferograms. The rotationality in (4) is a direct consequence of at least one independent processing step (multi-looking, filtering, PhU) and reveals stochastic and deterministic components [9].

3.1 Stochastic sources

Multi-looking or independent interferogram filtering may give rise to time inconsistencies (4). For instance, these sources are exploited by filtering approaches that force the wrapped phases to be irrotational in time [17]. Similarly, nonclosure triplets (4) may arise when independent [18] or hybrid [19] PhU tools are applied. Hence, time inconsistencies are even more remarkable when the latter two effects are jointly present [9].

3.1.1 A Heteroskedasticity-consistent Covariance Matrix for Phase Unwrapping Errors

In this subsection, we derive a method to design a covariance matrix for time-inconsistent PhU errors. First, considering the single-look case analysis and in the presence of time-inconsistent PhU errors, the following system of linear equations holds:

$$\mathbf{B}\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \Delta\Phi \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{B} is the design matrix, \mathbf{x} is the unknown vector that characterizes the ground deformations, $\Delta\Phi$ are the unwrapped InSAR phases, and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the vector of committed PhU errors. The Gauss-Markov theorem asserts that $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = (\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B})^{-1} \mathbf{B}^T \Delta\Phi$ is the best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE) of \mathbf{x} and it is obtained by solving (5) in the ordinary least-squares (OLS) sense under the assumption of homoscedasticity of the error vector $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ [20]. The homoscedastic condition holds when the PhU errors are assumed to be zero-mean i.i.d., but the assumption of a unique variance value is not generally enough. Thus, hereafter, the covariance matrix of time inconsistent PhU errors in the case of heteroscedasticity [20], adopting LS phase residuals $\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ [20] to obtain a proxy for covariances is addressed. Following

numerous studies in econometrics, which have thoroughly investigated the problems of errors heteroscedasticity by proposing efficient and robust estimators of the heteroscedasticity consistent covariance matrix (HCCM) [21], [22], we can adopt the HCCM estimator [22] and express the diagonal PhU errors covariance matrix:

$$\mathbf{C}_{PhU} = \text{diag} \left[\frac{\hat{\epsilon}^2}{(1-\mathbf{h})^2} \right]. \quad (6)$$

The concept behind the HCCM estimator is to use the squared LS phase residuals $\hat{\epsilon}^2$ to estimate the diagonal entries of the PhU errors covariance matrix \mathbf{C}_{PhU} , i.e., the different variance values of the time-inconsistent PhU errors. Note that \mathbf{h} is the vector of the principal diagonal elements of the following matrix $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B})^{-1} \mathbf{B}^T$, and it is used to better inflate the residuals $\hat{\epsilon}^2$ that are otherwise over-biased [22].

3.2 Systematic terms and Phase Bias Mitigation

In addition to deformation, ground targets may exhibit other subtle geophysical signals [6], [7] which can be treated as systemic contributions. The latter, mixed with other deterministic sources [9] are responsible for the recently observed phase bias [5]. SB ML InSAR, being much more coherent and therefore less noisy, can be sensitive to these subtle systemic contributions. More importantly, some of the signals contained in the nonclosure triplets (4), if adequately modelled, can be used to compensate for phase bias [9]–[11]. In this work, we apply the phase bias compensation method proposed in [9] that works directly on wrapped data and uses only nonclosure phase triplets. The method assumes that the deterministic signal of our interest reflected in the nonclosure triplets (finite second differences) is equal to or less than π (in the module) [9]. This assumption is verified in most of the cases because the triplets are finite second differences (acceleration terms). The acceleration values useful to reconstruct any "plausible" value of phase bias are far from exceeding π (in the module), also proven experimentally in [9], always keeping in mind that phase bias vanishes when the InSAR temporal baseline becomes larger [5].

Moreover, the methodology adopted does not assume a linear relationship between phase bias and temporal baseline. Also, it allows the bias to be calculated for each interferogram (for each time window), thus proposing a time-variant correction approach [9]. We invite readers to the following paper for an in-depth reading on the topic [9].

4 Experimental Results

To show some results, we selected an area between the Basilicata and Campania regions in southern Italy, which is characterized by a generally medium-to-low coherence and more prone to instabilities due to landslides, earthquakes, hydrogeological instability, and others. Moreover, the rural areas predominate at variance with built-up ones. The SAR

dataset consists of 385 Sentinel-1 A/B descending acquisitions processed in accordance with the above methods. First of all, **Figure 1** shows an InSAR covariance matrix due to decorrelation noise regarding a deforming target over a rural area (identifiable as a red asterisk in **Figure 2**), computed by following the SB-based approach detailed in Section 2.1; the axes of the covariance matrix show the variance-covariances in an ordered manner according to the combined temporal and perpendicular baseline values, thus highlighting the dependence between baselines increment and decorrelation.

Figure 1 Normalized InSAR variance-covariance matrix due to decorrelation effects computed on wrapped data using the method detailed in Section 2.1. The number of generated and showed SB-InSAR data is 8088.

Figure 2 Mean displacement velocity map of the selected test area imposing a maximum temporal baseline of 148 days. Only pixels characterized by temporal coherence larger than 0.7 are depicted.

A number of 8088 wrapped InSAR phases with a maximum temporal baseline of 148 days were generated. Then, we unwrapped the dataset [19] and computed the ground displacement InSAR products [3]; **Figure 2** shows the mean displacement velocity map of the investigated area. For the same pixel of interest, we applied the HCCM for

the PhU errors procedure described in Section 3.1.1. Furthermore, we used the simple error propagation law to transform from the PhU error covariance matrix of the InSAR phases to the same but expressed for the SAR time series. **Figure 3** shows the ground displacement time series and the error bars for each sample; note that the errors are due to time inconsistent PhU errors. However, since multi-look phases are being used, a small part of the estimated error bars is also due to decorrelation effects. Inspecting the plot, it can be seen that PhU errors are generally evenly distributed over the entire data set; this is mainly due to the least-squares solution that forces PhU errors to spread over all samples. This result would also seem significant for multigrid techniques [23]–[25]. Specifically, for areas affected by several PhU errors, it would be preferable not to use the ground deformation time series to obtain the residual high-frequency contributions (because they might be distorted) [23], [24], and then to use multigrid algorithms that allow the phase to be unwrapped directly at full spatial resolution [25].

Figure 3 Ground displacement time-series of the selected pixel located in a rural area (red asterisk in Figure 2). The error bars are computed using the HCCM for PhU errors described in Section 3.1.1.

Regarding the systemic terms highlighted in Section 3.2, we perform other experiments to further assess the capabilities of the phase bias compensation method in [9].

Figure 4 Systematic term experiments; application of the phase bias compensation method [9]. On the left, the bias-uncorrected ground deformation velocity differences were mapped using the SB networks at 6 and 148 days. The bias-corrected ground deformation velocity differences between the SB networks at 6 and 148 days are on the right map. Only pixels characterized by temporal coherence larger than 0.7 are depicted.

For this purpose, we calculated two mean velocity displacement maps using an SB network with a maximum temporal baseline of 6 days without phase bias compensation (with the original ML interferograms) and with phase bias compensation by the time-variant method [9] (with the corrected ML interferograms), respectively. **Figure 4** shows the differences between the reference map of 148 days (**Figure 1**) and the 6 days maps uncorrected (left panel) and correct (right panel), respectively. Inspecting the maps visible the bias on the displacement phase field estimation (left panel); the same does not occur if the compensation method is applied first (right panel).

5 Conclusion

Time inconsistencies in Mt-InSAR analyses could impact the retrieved deformation InSAR phase field. The causes can be both systemic and stochastic. We have addressed the direct consequences of the stochastic contributions by developing two statistical methods suited for decorrelation noise and PhU errors. More in deep, the technique for decorrelation noise exploits directional statistics and is mainly developed for SB approaches. In contrast, the one for PhU errors allows the errors to be treated more generally and specifically as independent but not identically distributed (heteroskedasticity generalization). On the systemic side, we applied a newly developed phase bias compensation algorithm [9] to compensate for this other source of deviation deterministically. The proposed methodologies have proven effective in reducing and highlighting the deviations (inconsistencies) that may occur in Mt-InSAR analyses. However, further investigations must be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of a heterogeneous variety of scenarios. For instance, when applying the proposed method for PhU errors in the case of ML analysis, it is crucial to remember that a small portion of inconsistencies could be due to the ML operator and, thus, the decorrelation sources. Therefore, it is crucial to work on separating into two distinct terms. Also challenging is the extraction of other geophysical signals of interest from the time-inconsistencies due to the systemic source; a few attempts have been made in this context (for example, to extract soil moisture [7], [8]), but it is not trivial since in the systemic term causing the phase bias several deterministic sources are mixed, moving with their trends and orders of magnitude. In conclusion, further development is needed to assess the full potential offered by these time-inconsistencies.

6 Literature

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